

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's Conversion to Buddhism and the Way out to Progress Society

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ABSTRACT

Dr. B.R.Ambedkar has put his mark on Indian society which millions of the downtrodden people have been somewhat have sustainability because of his efforts. So he was called the father of Indian Constitution. He remarked, "The religion which discriminates between two followers is partial and the religion which treats crores of its adherents worse than dogs and criminals and inflicts upon them insufferable disabilities is no religion at all. He wanted to have a religion in the sense of 'spiritual principles', truly 'universal' and applicable to all times, to all countries and to all races. He concluded that this religion must be destroyed and there was nothing irreligious in working for the destruction of such a religion. The newly converted Buddhists themselves were convinced that they were very inaccurate indeed and that the number of Buddhists in India was actually far greater than the census returns showed, and in this they were undoubtedly right, though perhaps not quite to the extent that some of them believed. Some of those who thus remained suspended in a kind of limbo, able neither really to leave the hell of Hinduism and caste nor really to enter the heaven of Buddhism and equality, were unwilling to declare themselves Buddhists because they were afraid that, if they did so, they would be subject to harassment by the more militant Caste Hindus, who in some places were actually attacking and killing the newly converted Buddhists for daring to renounce their ancestral religion. He wanted to have a religion in the sense of 'spiritual principles', truly 'universal' and applicable to all times, to all countries and to all races.

Key Words: Buddhists, Indian society, Indian Constitution, Converted, and Religion.

Introduction

Dr. B.R.Ambedkar was the molder of the modern Indian society through his Indian constitution. He has put his mark on Indian society which millions of the downtrodden people have been somewhat have sustainability because of his efforts. So he was called the father of Indian Constitution. According to Ambedkar, religion must be judged by social standards, based on social ethics.¹ He linked religion with the social well-being of the people. He remarked, "The religion which discriminates between two followers is partial and the religion which treats crores of its adherents worse than dogs and criminals and inflicts upon them insufferable disabilities is no religion at all."² He wanted to have a religion in the sense of 'spiritual principles', truly 'universal' and applicable to all times, to all countries and to all races."³

Fundamental principles of social life

He treated Hinduism as "a mass of sacrificial, societal, political and sanitary rules and regulations; all mixed up."⁴ Ambedkar has given four characteristics of religion (1)Religion in the sense of morality, must remain the governing principle in every society, (2) Religion, if it is to function, must be in accord with reason which is merely another name for science. (3.) Its moral code must recognise the fundamental tenets of liberty, equality and fraternity. Unless a religion recognises these three fundamental principles of social life, it will be doomed. (4) Religion must not sanctify or ennoble poverty.⁵ According to him, "What is called religion by Hindus is nothing but a multitude of commands and prohibitions."⁶ He has enumerated the evils of Hindu religion as follows (1) It has deprived moral life of freedom; (2) It has only conformity to commands; (3) The laws are inequitous in that they are not the same for one class as for another. This code had the finality. He concluded that this religion must be destroyed and there was nothing irreligious in working for the destruction of such a religion.⁷ Ambedkar wanted a change from a 'religion of rules' to a religion of principles', a change required before it could be a 'true religion'. Among his requirements were "(1) one standard book of Hindu religion; (2) no hereditary priesthood, but an examination system open to all; (3) state sanads (permits) required for priests ;(4) a limit by law on the number of priests; (5) state supervision of the priests' morals, beliefs and worship."⁸

According to Ambedkar “Religion, in the sense of spiritual principles” truly ‘universal’ applicable to all times, to all countries and to all races. That such was indeed the case was evident from an article on ‘The Buddha and the Future of His Religion’ which Ambedkar contributed to the April-May issue of the *Maha Bodhi*, the journal of the Maha Bodhi Society. In this important article, which showed how deeply he had been thinking about Buddhism, Ambedkar even went so far as to declare that Buddhism was the only religion which the world could have. ‘If the new world – which be it realized is very different from the old must have a religion and the new world needs a religion far more than the old world did –then it can only be the religion of the Buddha.’ Ambedkar considered the foundations of religion to be essential to life and practices of society. According to him, religion was a part of one's "social inheritance". He wanted religion, but he did not want hypocrisy in the name of religion. Religion, to him, was the driving force for human activity. He remarked, "Man cannot live by bread alone. He has a mind which needs food for the thought."⁹

Ambedkar's journey to Buddhism

Ambedkar's journey to Buddhism can be traced over a span of about forty years. At the age of sixteen Keluskar gave him a copy of the life of Gautam Buddha. In the 30 years up to 1945 he had bitter experiences of caste Hindus, and he tried his utmost to have separate electorates—an attempt to isolate Scheduled Castes completely from Hindus. In 1945 he attended a Buddhist conference. On 20th June 1946, on behalf of People's Education Society, he started a college and named it Siddharth College. In 1948, he wrote a foreword to L. Narasu's book—'The Essence of Buddhism'. In 1950, he took part in the first Modern Buddhist procession in Delhi. In December 1954, he took part in the Third World Federation of Buddhists. It is said that there he made up his mind to embrace Buddhism. Ambedkar was inclined towards Buddhism openly from May 1956. On 24th May 1956 he declared on the day of Buddha Jayanti celebrations at Nare Park in Bombay that he would embrace Buddhism in October 1956. On 23rd September 1956, he issued a press note announcing that his conversion to Buddhism would take place at Nagpur on the Dassahra day, 14th October 1956 between 9 and 11 a.m. He himself preferred Nagpur which was a historic town where the Buddhist Nagas flourished in ancient times.

D.C. Ahir claimed that due to Ambedkar's influence as the architect of India's Constitution the Asoka Chakra (the wheel of law) was put on the 1 flag of India, and the Lions from the Asoka pillar at Sarnath were adopted as the National Emblem.¹⁰

A question was raised by many critics when Ambedkar resolved to renounce Hinduism. Why had he waited for a long period of twenty years? It is said that he deliberately waited up to the 2500th birthday of Buddha. B.S. Murthy answered this question. He remarked, "The only answer seems to be that he dearly loved all that was good in Hinduism."¹¹ The insulting treatment at the hands of the Hindus; the denial of Sanskrit and Vedic learning; his experiences in Baroda and in the Bombay Bar—all these convinced him that the untouchables would never receive just treatment in Hindu Dharma and Hindu Society. He was sure that individual and group mobility were difficult within the Hindu social system for the untouchables. He was aware that compassion, equality and freedom were not to be found in Hindu religion. He rejected renunciation. He was attracted towards Buddhism because of its moral basis of equality, justice and wide basis of humanitarianism. Srinivasan, Jagjivan Ram and M. C. Rajah rejected the idea of conversion. In the All Bombay District Mahar Conference, 30-31 May 1936, Ambedkar characterised the problem of untouchability as a problem of class strife. He thought that to remain in Hinduism and attempt to abolish caste system was like sweetening poison. For this he emphasised to look for power from some source outside the Hindu fold.

Observation about Dhamma

Ambedkar regarded Dhamma as religion. He observed, "Religion is personal, contrary to this, Dhamma is social." He described Dhamma as righteousness, right relations between man and man in all spheres of life. The Buddhist way of life aimed at the moral regeneration and social emancipation of all human beings. According to him, there were only four preceptors— Shri Krishna, Buddha, Christ and Mohammed. Buddha appealed to him most as he always preached that his disciples should not obey his commands but should follow the dictates of their conscience. There is no god in Buddhism, but the place of god is taken by morality

The merits of Buddhist philosophy are given as follows:—(a) Buddhism demands living existence and a life divine attainable here and now—and not after death, (b) It is a realism—never an idealism, (c) It upholds liberty, equality, truth and justice—it pours on humanity love and peace, (d) It is dynamic, scientific and all-embracing, (e) Its explanation of life and its meaning and purpose of birth and its nature, of death and its aftermath is very clear, intelligible and logical, (f) Above all, man is the centre of its study and examination, not anything outside him. On the contrary, the static nature of Hindu Dharma and society was emphasized as below: (a) Hindu Society is as it was in B.C. with trivial modifications, (b) Untouchability is recognised by the Hindu religion; it is deeply rooted in Hindu Society, (c) Caste is the corner-stone to the arch of Hinduism."¹² According to Ambedkar, Hinduism and Buddhism differed in three vital aspects. In Hindu religion, there is Ishwar (God), Atma (soul), and Varna system; in Buddhism, there is no Ishwar, soul and caste or Varna system. Ambedkar was always of the view that social and human reconstruction needed religious basis.¹³ In a speech on the British Broadcasting Corporation he outlined his preference of Buddhism to Hinduism. He preferred Buddhism because it gave three principles in combination which no other religion gave. Buddhism teaches Prajna (understanding against superstition and i.e. super natural), Karuna (Love), and Samata (equality). He preferred Buddhism because like Christianity it affords hope to the down-trodden.¹⁴ According to him; Buddhism was a true religion because it led to a life guided by the three principles of knowledge, right path and compassion. He remarked, "Buddhism is a part and parcel of Bharatiya Culture. I have taken care that my conversion will not harm the tradition of the culture and history of this land."¹⁵

He said in an interview on 13th October 1956 at Nagpur that he would not remain a member of the S.C.F. after conversion to Buddhism. There were two mottos before him Budham Saranam Gachami means 'I am surrendering myself to the person possessed of knowledge' ; and the other is Sangham Saranam Gachami I am surrendering myself to Sanghs- Guilds. Sangh means social life; to him Buddha was a great socialist of his times. He was a rationalist and he rooted out the monopoly of Brahmins. After his conversion to

Buddhism on 14th October 1956, Ambedkar said that, by discarding ancient religion which stood for inequality and oppression he was reborn that day and felt as if liberated from hell. He was deeply moved when he said, "I renounce Hinduism." He reminded his followers of his vow taken in 1935 that 'even though I am born a Hindu I will not die a Hindu'. He fulfilled his vow. He had the satisfaction of having accomplished a great deed in establishing the revival of Buddhism in India.

India today is beset with numerous problems- social, economic, political and religious- threatening the very existence and integrity of the millions, particularly the backward, the downtrodden and the powerless. Ambedkar as we know was the champion of the cause of the underprivileged and downtrodden, of their protection against social injustice of the uplift from the most demeaning level of existence as untouchables. There are at present about 20% Untouchables in Indian population, the vast majority of who are underprivileged in every sense of the term. Each year between four and five hundred of them are murdered by the Caste Hindu compatriots, while thousands more are beaten, raped, and tortured and their homes looted and burned. The number of them is not only subject to social, economic, and religious discrimination but daily suffer personal harassment and humiliation

According to professor Ghurye the outstanding features of Hindu society are: (1) Segmental division of society,(2) Hierarchy, (3)restrictions on feeding and social intercourse;(4) civil and religious disabilities and privileges of the different sections,(5) lack of unrestricted choice of occupation and (6)restriction on marriage—endogamy as the essence of the caste system². In the same way Dr.M.N.Srinivas, said the three main axes of power in the caste system are the ritual, the economic and the political ones and the possession of power in any one sphere usually leads to the acquisition of power in the other two¹⁶.

Ambedkar's first recorded contact with Buddhism occurred in 1908, when he was sixteen. He had just passed the matriculation examination of Bombay University, and so extraordinary an achievement was this for an untouchable boy that the Mahars celebrated the occasion with a public meeting in his honour. The meeting was held in Bombay under the presidency of S.K. Bole, a well known social reformer from the Bhandari community who, some two decades later, was to co-operate with Ambedkar in the Chowdar Tank campaign. Among the

speakers at the meeting was a local high school teacher called Krishnaji Arjun Keluskar. Though a Maharashtra Brahmin by birth Keluskar was a man of liberal views and an admirer of the Buddha. He had, in fact, recently published a life of the Buddha in Marathi, and a copy of this work he now presented to the young Ambedkar. Being nothing if not an avid reader, the new matriculate lost no time in devouring the book, and there is no doubt that the sublime story of the Buddha's renunciation of all earthly ties, his search for truth, his eventual attainment of Enlightenment, and his compassionate activity on behalf of his fellow men, left an indelible impression on his mind. Keluskar, for his part, continued to take a keen interest in the brilliant untouchable boy, and it was through his good offices that, three years later, the Maharaja Gaekwad of Baroda granted Ambedkar the scholarship that enabled him to continue his education. That a liberal-minded Brahmin like Keluskar should have written and published a life of the Buddha was a sign of the times. For at least seven or eight centuries Buddhism had been unknown in India, the land of its birth, and the name of the Buddha himself had lingered on only as that of an alleged incarnation of the god Vishnu who had taken birth for the express purpose of misleading the asuras or anti-gods with a false teaching. But the darkness was lifting. Thanks to the labours of orientalists like James Princep and archaeologists like Alexander Cunningham, as well as to the more popular activities of the Theosophists.

By the end of the nineteenth century the main events of the Buddha's career and the general nature of his teaching had begun to penetrate the consciousness of English-educated Hindus and, by their means, to percolate through the rest of society. In eastern India the founding of the Buddhist Text Society in Calcutta in 1892 gave an impetus to the scholarly study of Buddhism, while Anagarika Dharmapala's work for the resuscitation of Bodh-gaya, where the Buddha had gained Enlightenment, helped to remind people of the greatness of India's Buddhist heritage. The precise nature of Keluskar's relation to all these developments is difficult to ascertain, but it is clear that the worthy Brahmin was one of those who had come under the influence of the movement of Buddhist revival and that the book he presented to the sixteen-year-old Ambedkar was a product of that influence. Thus the book represented not only Ambedkar's first contact with Buddhism; it also represented his first contact with the movement of which he himself was to be the brightest ornament.

But Ambedkar's closeness to Buddhism was not just in respect of certain principles; it was also a closeness of personal sympathy. In other words, the closeness was not only intellectual but emotional. Two days after the burning of the *Manusmriti* Ambedkar and his entourage went on an expedition to a place in the neighborhood of Mahad in order to see the excavations of some ruins that were believed to date from the time of the Buddha. Deeply moved by the sight of the sculptures that had been unearthed, Ambedkar described to the members of his entourage how the Buddha's disciples had lived lives of poverty and chastity and selflessly devoted themselves to the service of the community. In a reverential mood, he asked them not to sit on the ancient stone benches that formed part of the ruins since these may have been the seats of Buddhist monks. It was almost as though he felt himself to be back in the days when Buddhism flourished in India and when Buddhist monks and monasteries were to be seen in every part of his beloved Maharashtra. The six years that followed the Chowdar Tank campaign were years of vacillation. Sometimes it seemed that Ambedkar had travelled a long way from Hinduism, whether or not in the direction of some other religion, and sometimes it seemed that he had not. Sometimes he even appeared to be retracing his steps. Speaking at Jalgaon in May 1929, at a conference called by the Depressed Classes of the Central Provinces and Berar, he bluntly told his hearers that it was quite impossible for them to get rid of their disabilities so long as they remained in the Hindu fold and a resolution was passed to that effect. Fifteen months later, however, addressing the All-India Depressed Classes Congress in Nagpur, he declared that whatever hardships the Caste Hindus inflicted on him he would not abjure the Hindu religion. By 1933 the question of his abjuring Hinduism had become rather an academic one, for in February of that year he told Mahatma Gandhi that he could not honestly call himself a Hindu. Why, he demanded, should he be proud of that religion which condemned him to a position of degradation?

The truth of the matter was that for Ambedkar and his followers the question of their renouncing Hinduism was a difficult and complex one, with all kinds of social, economic, and political implications, and the untouchable leader tended to move nearer to, or farther away from, the taking of so drastic a step according to whether a change of heart on the part of the Caste Hindus seemed more, or less, likely. In the end, after years of unsuccessful struggle for the basic human rights of his people, he was forced to recognize that there was going to be no change of

heart on the part of the Caste Hindus, and that the casteless, 'Protestant' Hinduism of which he had sometimes spoken so enthusiastically was only a dream. Indeed, it was a contradiction in terms. Hinduism and the caste system were inseparable, and since the outcaste was a by-product of the caste system – for where there were castes there were outcastes – it followed that there could be no emancipation for the Untouchables within the caste system and, therefore, no emancipation for them within Hinduism. If they wanted to rid themselves of their age-old disabilities they had no alternative but to renounce the religion into which they had been born.

As Ambedkar became increasingly convinced that renunciation of Hinduism was the way forward for him and his people the rumours began to spread, and in the summer of 1933 he had to assure an anxious correspondent that he was not about to become a convert to Islam. Writing from London, where he had gone as a delegate to the parliamentary select committee on Indian.

Basic human rights as members of the Hindu community

The explosion took place at Yeola on 13 October 1935, and it rocked Hindu India in a way that even the burning of the *Manusmriti* had not done. The occasion was a conference which, it was announced, the leaders of the Depressed Classes had convened to review the social and political situation in the light of their ten-year-old struggle and the coming constitutional reforms. 10,000 Untouchables of all shades of opinion attended, including representatives from the Central Provinces and the adjoining princely states, and Ambedkar delivered a powerful and impassioned speech in which he described the hardships suffered by the Depressed Classes in all spheres of life, whether social, economic, educational, or political, and spoke bitterly of the failure of their attempts to secure their basic human rights as members of the Hindu community. The Kalaram Temple campaign, for example, had been a complete failure and a waste of time and energy. The time had therefore come for them to settle the matter once and for all. Since the disabilities under which they laboured were the direct result of their membership of the Hindu community, they should sever their connections with Hinduism and seek solace and self-respect in another religion. As for himself, it was his misfortune that he had been born an untouchable Hindu. *That* was beyond his power to prevent, but it was certainly within his power to refuse to

live under ignoble and humiliating conditions. ‘I therefore solemnly assure you,’ he declared, ‘that though I have been born a Hindu I will not die a Hindu

Brahmin rule were not easily forgotten. In the early 1850s a fourteen-year-old untouchable girl (not a Mahar but a Mang) who was attending Jyotirao Phooley’s school for low-caste girls in Poona wrote an essay on the condition of the Mahars and Mangs. In this essay she observed, inter alia: ‘Formerly we were buried alive in the foundations of buildings. We were not allowed to pass by the Talimkhana. If any man was found to do so, his head was cut off playfully. We were not allowed to read and write. If [Peshwa] Bajirao II came to know about such a case, he would indignantly say: “What! If Mahars and Mangs learn to read and write, are the Brahmins to hand over their writing work to them and to go round shaving widows [i.e. working as barbers, who were of Shudra caste] with their bags hanging from their shoulders?” God has bestowed on us the rule of the British and our grievances are redressed. Nobody harasses us now. Nobody hangs us. Nobody buries us alive. Our progeny can live now. We can now wear clothes; can put on cloth around our body. Everybody is at liberty to live according to his means. No bars, no taboos, no restrictions. Even the bazaar at the Gultekadi is open to us.’¹⁷

He himself was, as usual, sufficiently outward-looking. After the conclusion of the conference he not only saw as much as he could of the ceremonies and rituals of Ceylon Buddhism but found time to address the Young Men’s Buddhist Association, Colombo, on ‘The Rise and Fall of Buddhism in India’. Buddhism had not disappeared from India, he asserted. Though its material form had disappeared, as a spiritual force it still existed. What had led to the decline of Buddhism in India was not clear. He himself was still studying the subject, but he believed that Buddhism had faded away in India because of the rise of Vaishnavism and Shivaism and because of the Muslim invasion of India. ‘When Alla-ud-din marched into Bihar, he killed five to six thousand Bhikkhus. The remaining Buddhist monks fled to neighbouring countries like China, Nepal, and Tibet. Efforts were, subsequently, made by Buddhists of India to raise another priesthood in order to revive Buddhism. But these failed as by then ninety per cent of the people had embraced Hinduism.’ Answering the question why Hinduism had survived in India and Buddhism had died, Ambedkar observed, ‘Buddhism as a religion is difficult to practise while Hinduism is not.’¹⁸ Shortly afterwards he addressed a meeting in the Colombo Town Hall and appealed to the Untouchables there to embrace Buddhism, saying that

there was no need for them to have a separate organization. He also urged the Buddhists of Ceylon to accept the Untouchables and look after their Interests with paternal care. Ambedkar's visit to Ceylon naturally attracted a good deal of attention, and on his return to India some of his opponents accused him of being an opportunist. Replying to the charge in the course of a speech delivered under the auspices of the Bombay Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society on 25 July he denied that he was an opportunist with regard to his views on Buddhism and said that he had been interested in Buddhism since his boyhood. Later in the year, on 29 September, he returned to the question of conversion in a way that showed how broad his vision was and how much he had the welfare of the whole country at heart. Speaking at the Japanese Buddhist Temple, Worli (Bombay), he deprecated the idea that political independence meant the end of all the Country's ills. So long as there was no purity, wrongdoing and utter disregard of morals would continue in everyday life; and as long as man did not know how to behave with man, India could never be prosperous. 'To end all these troubles, India must embrace Buddhism', he declared. 'Buddhism is the only religion based upon ethical principles and teaches how to work for the wellbeing of the common man.'¹⁹ As if to underline the urgency of the situation, he concluded his speech by declaring that he would devote the rest of his life to the revival and spread of Buddhism. This was more easily said than done.

As Minister for Law, Ambedkar was responsible for piloting the Hindu Code Bill through the Constituent Assembly, besides which the poor state of his health was giving increasing cause for concern. But though he was not, as yet, able to devote himself to the revival and spread of Buddhism his mind was made up, and speaking at the Buddha Vihara, New Delhi, in May 1951, he declared, 'If the rest of the Hindu society does not co-operate, then we, the members of the Scheduled Castes, will go on our own and try once again to bring back Buddhism to its former glory and prestige in this country.'²⁰ Buddhism could not be restored to its former glory, however, whether by the members of the Scheduled Castes or anyone else, so long as the charges that were often leveled against it were allowed to remain unanswered. A Hindu author writing in *Eve's Weekly* having claimed that it was the Buddhist theory that had first thrust women into the background and that the Buddha was ever exhorting men to beware of women, Ambedkar therefore contributed to the April-May issue of the *Maha Bodhi* a pungent and scholarly article entitled 'The Rise and Fall of the Hindu Woman. Who was Responsible for it?' In this article he

showed conclusively that it was not the Buddha who was responsible for the downfall of the Hindu woman but the Hindu law-giver Manu, the author of the *Manusmriti*. According to Ambedkar, the Buddha endeavoured to ennoble woman and raise her to the level of man.

Baba Saheb Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar died

Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar died in the early hours of 6 December, 1956 and at 7.30 p.m. the following day his body was cremated in Bombay, which had been his headquarters for the greater part of his career and where he still had the greatest number of followers. 5,00,000 people joined the two mile long funeral procession, which took four hours to make its way from 'Rajagriha', Ambedkar's residence in Dadar, to the local burning ghat, and was the biggest such procession the city had ever seen. Afterwards more than 1,00,000 of those who had witnessed the cremation escorted the great leader's ashes back to 'Rajagriha'. Before leaving the burning ghat, however, they insisted on fulfilling 'Baba Saheb's' wishes and embracing Buddhism. An impromptu conversion ceremony was accordingly held, and one of the Bhikkhus who was present administered the Three Refuges and Five Precepts to all 1, 00,000 of them on the spot.

From Bombay a portion of the ashes was taken to Delhi where, a week later, a conversion ceremony was held at which 30,000 people were initiated into Buddhism. These same ashes having been divided in their turn and a portion handed over to Ambedkar's followers in Agra a similar ceremony was held in that city too. This time 2, 00,000 people were initiated into Buddhism. Thus the great movement of mass conversion that had been inaugurated in Nagpur only six weeks earlier continued unabated. Between 7 December 1956 and 10 February 1957 conversion ceremonies were in fact held not only in Bombay, Delhi, and Agra but in more than twenty different towns and cities, most of them within the boundaries of the present day State of Maharashtra, with the result that by the end of that period the number of ex-untouchable Buddhists had risen from 7,50,000 – the number converted by Ambedkar himself in Nagpur and Chanda – to well over 40,00,000.²¹ Most of the ceremonies were organized by branches of the Indian Buddhist Society, the body re-founded by Ambedkar in 1955, and the new converts were received into the Buddhist fold either by a leading member of the Republican Party (some of whose office bearers doubled as office-bearers of the Indian Buddhist Society) or by a Sinhalese or Indian Bhikkhu from the Maha Bodhi Society. Sometimes the new converts would be

received into the Buddhist fold by the politician and the Bhikkhu jointly, with the Bhikkhu administering the Three Refuges and Five Precepts and the politician administering the twenty-two vows.

After 10 February 1957, however, the conversion movement was suspended until after the March general elections – the same elections on account of which some of Ambedkar's lieutenants had wanted him to postpone the original mass conversion ceremony. The expectation was that when the elections were over the conversion movement would be not only continued but intensified. This did not, unfortunately, prove to be the case. Though conversion ceremonies indeed continued to be held all over central and western India, and even farther afield, with the exception of that held at Aligarh on 13 April, when 2,00,000 people embraced Buddhism, they were on the whole smaller and less spectacular affairs than before. This may have been due to the fact that the conversion movement, having been virtually suspended for two crucial months, had now lost much of its original impetus and that what had been lost could not easily be regained. It may equally have been due to the fact that the movement had reached what were, for the time being, its natural limits. Though Ambedkar was held in the highest esteem by all the untouchable communities of India his influence was greatest within his own Mahar community, and it was the Mahars who had responded most enthusiastically to his call to embrace Buddhism. Once the Mahars had been converted, therefore, the conversion movement naturally slowed down, the more especially since Ambedkar himself was no longer present to convince the other untouchable communities of the rightness of the step he had taken and persuades them to do likewise.

Conclusion

The fact that the conversion movement had reached its natural limits by the beginning of 1957 was reflected in the official statistics. According to the 1961 census returns there were 32,50,227 Buddhists in India, an increase of 1,671 per cent over the 1951 figure of whom 27,89,501 were to be found in Maharashtra as compared with 2,489 ten years earlier. The increase in the number of Buddhists in Maharashtra was thus out of all proportion to the increase in the rest of the country. By 1971, however, the figures had risen only very slightly and there were altogether 38,12,325 registered Buddhists in India, from which fact it was clear that even

though a number of conversion ceremonies had been held outside Maharashtra the movement of mass conversion among the Mahars had not been followed by any corresponding movement among the other untouchable communities.

Not that the statistics in question were completely accurate. The newly converted Buddhists themselves were convinced that they were very inaccurate indeed and that the number of Buddhists in India was actually far greater than the census returns showed, and in this they were undoubtedly right, though perhaps not quite to the extent that some of them believed. According to one source, by March 1959 ‘nearly 15 to 20 million Untouchables had embraced Buddhism’.²² There were two reasons for the discrepancy between the official figures, on the one hand, and the facts as known to the Buddhists themselves on the other. In the first place the census-takers, most of whom were Caste Hindus, in some cases deliberately enumerated Buddhists as Hindus in order to minimize the extent, and therefore the significance, of the conversion movement. In the second place, many of those who had embraced Buddhism at one or another of the conversion ceremonies, and who therefore appeared in the Buddhists’ own statistics, did not officially declare themselves as Buddhists, and hence were not included as such in the census returns. Some of those who thus remained suspended in a kind of limbo, able neither really to leave the hell of Hinduism and caste nor really to enter the heaven of Buddhism and equality, were unwilling to declare themselves Buddhists because they were afraid that, if they did so, they would be subject to harassment by the more militant Caste Hindus, who in some places were actually attacking and killing the newly converted Buddhists for daring to renounce their ancestral religion. Such was the Great Buddhism isolated in India. But with the great efforts of Dr.B.R.Ambedkar that was reborn in our country.

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